

A parametric LCA platform for modelling environmental impacts in plant protein processing: Application to pea, soy, and wheat protein isolates and concentrates

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ABSTRACT

The central dietary role of proteins and the high environmental burden of animal-based food require a transition to more sustainable protein sources. Plant protein extracts are the primary commercial alternatives, yet their environmental impacts remain poorly quantified. We present the first regionalized life cycle assessment of soy, pea, and wheat proteins, based on a harmonized modelling platform to evaluate 19 global value chains supplying the European market. The model relies on fully parameterized foreground inventories to assess the uncertainty and model sensitivity related to variable process efficiencies, methodological choices (e.g., economic allocation), and transport distances through Monte-Carlo analysis. Water stress, health impacts through particulate matter emissions, and land-use-related biodiversity loss were quantified based on country-specific characterization factors along with global warming impacts. Resulting environmental impacts vary by up to three orders of magnitude. These wide ranges underscore how regional factors like energy systems and climatic conditions critically determine environmental footprints, necessitating transparency for downstream manufacturers. Additionally, results for single value chains varied by a factor of 1.5 to 3, highlighting the relevance of efficient process design for minimizing environmental impacts. A global sensitivity analysis reveals that protein content in raw materials, extraction yields, renewable energy, and transport are the primary leverage points for reducing impacts across all value chains. Our publicly available modelling platform and dataset can readily be applied to other plant protein value chains to optimize protein processing in the future.

1. Introduction

Given the central role of proteins in human diets and the high environmental burdens of animal-based food, the protein transition is an integral part of the urgently needed food system transformation (Duluins and Baret, 2024; Willett et al., 2019). It describes a dietary shift aimed at partially replacing animal-based protein sources with alternatives from plants, insects, microorganisms, or cultivated animal cells. The largest environmental gains are expected from the replacement of meat products, particularly from ruminants such as beef and lamb (Clark et al., 2022; Poore and Nemecek, 2018). To facilitate such a transition for consumers, the food industry has turned towards the development of substitutes that aim to mimic the taste, appearance, and functionality of

conventional meat products (Nezlek and Forestell, 2022). To date, meat substitutes are largely based on concentrates and isolates from pea, soy, and wheat, which are the main protein sources in over 60 % of available products (Siegrist et al., 2024).

The environmental impact of cultivation is relatively well-studied for most plant-based ingredients. In life cycle assessment (LCA) databases, the inventory data for common crops such as pea, soy, and wheat are often available for multiple geographical regions and different cropping systems (Blonk et al., 2022; Wernet et al., 2016). At the same time, the scientific evidence for the environmental impact of protein processing is limited to a few case studies of the most established ingredients (Allotey et al., 2023; Smetana et al., 2023). A common limitation is access to data on the capacity and utility consumption of industrial plants and their disclosure. Available studies often rely either on confidential inventories

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Nomenclature	
P	Parameter
E	Energy
ele	electricity
m	mass flow
Dist	distance
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
SPC	Soy Protein Concentrate
SPI	Soy Protein Isolate
PPC	Pea Protein Concentrate
PPI	Pea Protein Isolate
WG	Wheat Gluten
PM-HI	Particulate Matter-related Health Impacts
WS	Water Stress
LU-BL	Land-Use-related Biodiversity Loss
GW	Global Warming
DALY	Disability Adjusted Life Years
PDF	Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species

from industry partners or lab- and pilot-scale data (Allotey et al., 2024; Detzel et al., 2022; Fresán et al., 2019; Heller and Keoleian, 2018; Heusala et al., 2020; Röder et al., 2022). The latter was sometimes projected to estimate industry-relevant impacts, leading to additional uncertainty. Furthermore, variable methodological choices concerning,

e.g., system boundaries and impact assessment methods, and a limited application of uncertainty and sensitivity analyses in the existing case studies make it difficult to understand how environmental impacts of protein processing are influenced by process variability, e.g., site-specific protein yields and energy demands, as well as regional differences such as water stress, and energy production systems (Allotey et al., 2023). However, such information is essential for more accurate sustainability assessments of products, e.g., meat substitutes, diets, and the protein transition alike.

We address this knowledge gap through a harmonized parametric LCA modelling platform that considers both the variability and regional specificity of protein processing and provides tools for extensive uncertainty and sensitivity analyses of the foreground system. We demonstrate its operability for the five most used plant protein ingredients, namely soy protein concentrate (SPC) and isolate (SPI), pea protein concentrate (PPC) and isolate (PPI), and wheat gluten (WG) (Siegrist et al., 2024). As a result, this study is the first to present robust estimates for regionalized impacts related to human health through particulate matter formation (PM-HI), water stress (WS), and land use-driven biodiversity loss (LU-BL), along with global warming (GW) impacts based on realistic global production scenarios for the European market. As the protein processing of most plant-based ingredients is based on similar unit operations (Allotey et al., 2022; Schutyser and van der Goot, 2011; Singh et al., 2022), we expect the collected process parameters and the modelling platform to be useful resources for future LCAs of other plant-based ingredients. They can readily be adapted to similar value chains and different geographical contexts.

Fig. 1. Overview of the conceptual modelling structure for protein processing. The map at the bottom illustrates the value chains that were modelled for the case studies.

2. Methods

2.1. Goal and scope

The attributional LCA model was applied to quantify the environmental impacts of common plant protein value chains for the European market. The considered value chains are illustrated at the bottom of Fig. 1 and summarized in Table S.1. We selected them based on the location of existing processing companies (Good Food Institute, 2025) and agricultural trade statistics of the ingredients from the FAO (FAO, 2025). To have a fair comparison, we assumed that all protein ingredients were delivered to the same country, i.e., Switzerland, for further application, e.g., the manufacturing of meat substitutes. Due to the versatile applications of plant proteins, this stage was not included in the modelled system. Hence, the system boundaries were cradle-to-gate, including all processes from raw material extraction up to the point where the refined protein is delivered to the country of use.

Capital goods in the foreground model were excluded due to a lack of reliable data and their comparatively small contribution to the impacts of agricultural and food products (Eickelkamp, 2015; Frischknecht et al., 2007). Where applicable, treatment for biowaste and wastewater was modelled (see SI2). Further, plant protein processing includes many multi-output processes, e.g., starch and protein fractions, which pose an allocation problem. Although recommended by ISO 14040:2006 (International Organization for Standardization, 2006), substitution and system expansion strategies to avoid allocation were not practical solutions because reference products, such as other starches or fats, would often originate from multi-output processes themselves. Furthermore, it was important to distinguish between edible products and non-food side-streams such as hulls or fibers. Thus, we preferred economic over mass-based allocation to approximate differences in product quality through market values. We used two functional units, namely 1 kg of product and 1 kg of protein. The former was applied to contextualize the results since 1 kg of product was commonly used as a functional unit in existing studies on plant protein processing. The latter was selected because it reflects the main nutritional function of protein powders. Applied allocation parameters and protein contents can be found in SI2. To account for variable market prices and protein contents in the final products, they were both modelled as parameters (see section 2.6). In other words, results were not simply scaled by fixed allocation factors or protein contents. Instead, the results reflect the uncertainty associated with these parameters.

2.2. System mapping and process identification

Table 1 summarizes the unit processes that were considered in the manufacturing of each protein ingredient. Although there are other optional pretreatment steps for the harvested dry seeds, such as blanching, only the essential cleaning and dehulling steps for peas and soybeans were modelled, while no pretreatment was considered for wheat before milling (Allotey et al., 2022; Deak et al., 2008; Maningat et al., 2009). Compared to peas and wheat, dehulled soybeans are not dry milled but enter directly a defatting phase, which includes conditioning, flaking, defatting, and desolventizing. Defatting results in the co-products of soybean oil and soymeal. Here, the commonly used

hexane-based solvent extraction was modelled (Deak et al., 2008). PPC is generally obtained through various dry fractionation methods, which separate the milled peas into a starch- and protein-rich fraction. For this study, the air classification method was modelled (Allotey et al., 2022). PPI and SPI are commonly produced through isoelectric precipitation. The protein of the milled peas or defatted soymeal is first solubilized at slightly alkaline pH before it is precipitated by acidification to the isoelectric point at around pH 4.5 (Allotey et al., 2022; Berk, 1992). For peas, this process yields the co-products PPI and pea starch isolate, as well as a fiber-rich side-stream. For soy, the outputs are SPI and spent flakes, which can be used as animal feed. Both processes further produce a liquid supernatant, i.e., whey, which is often treated as effluent (Allotey et al., 2022; Berk, 1992). There are multiple established processes for separating starch and gluten in wheat flour. For this study, we selected the high-pressure disintegration process because it is the most established approach in Europe (Sayaslan, 2004). An alcohol wash was modelled for the production of SPC (Berk, 1992).

2.3. Material flow analysis and life cycle inventory

A complete data inventory can be found in SI2, together with literature sources and process flow diagrams for all value chains. Since resource use and emissions from the cultivation phase of pea, soy, and wheat are relatively well documented and not the primary focus of this study, we used data from the agrifootprint v.6.3 (Blonk et al., 2022) background database (cut-off system; hereafter referred to as agrifootprint) to model the cultivation and initial drying phase. We consulted scientific literature, the agrifootprint database, and equipment specification sheets from machine manufacturers to estimate the range of material and energy flows for the pretreatment steps and milling operations on an industrial scale. The defatting process for soybeans has already been investigated at an industrial scale by several studies (Castanheira et al., 2015; Cheng et al., 2018; Dalgaard et al., 2008; Omni Tech International, 2010; Sheehan et al., 1998). Therefore, we harmonized the reported data, i.e., aligned it in terms of system boundaries and reference flow (see SI2), and directly used it to estimate the material and energy flows involved in the defatting of soybeans. Due to the limited availability of scientific studies focusing on industry-scale protein concentration and isolation steps, they were constructed in a bottom-up approach. First, we consulted patents, scientific literature, industry information, and expert inputs to identify the necessary processing steps, equipment, and material flows. In a second step, we estimated the specific energy requirements for each piece of machinery based on equipment specification sheets and scientific literature. In the absence of any other information source, we relied on thermodynamic calculations to estimate the energy requirements of certain process steps (see SI2). Wherever possible, we collected industry-scale data and ranges of process parameter values.

2.4. Parametric LCA model

The parametric LCA model was built on the open-source Python-based libraries Brightway2 and lca_algebraic. The former offers functions for advanced LCA database management and calculations (Mutel, 2017). The latter was designed as an add-on to Brightway2 to increase

Table 1

Included unit processes in the models for the considered protein sources: pea protein concentrate (PPC) and isolate (PPI), soy protein concentrate (SPC) and isolate (SPI), and wheat gluten (WG).

	Cultivation	Pretreatment	Milling	Defatting	Air classification	Isoelectric precipitation	Alcohol wash	Gluten wash
PPC	x	x	x		x			
PPI	x	x	x			x		
SPC	x	x		x			x	
SPI	x	x		x		x		
WG	x		x					x

the computational speed of Monte-Carlo simulations for uncertainty and global sensitivity analysis (Jolivet et al., 2021). Further, *lca_algebraic* allows for the creation of parametrized foreground inventories that respect parameter interactions along the entire value chain (see section 2.6). The parametrized inventories were prepared in .csv files, which were read by the created model code to automatically generate location-specific foreground inventories (see GitHub: https://github.com/siegarmi/Parametric_LCA_plant_proteins). The model further linked the foreground inventories to the ecoinvent v.3.10 (Wernet et al., 2016) background database (cut-off; hereafter referred to as ecoinvent) and the agrifootprint database, which were required, e.g., for energy inputs, transport, waste treatment, and primary crop production. If needed, the model adapted these background datasets to the geographic scope of interest, e.g., by changing electricity mixes.

2.5. Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis

All LCA calculations were conducted in the form of Monte-Carlo simulations with 100'000 runs to assess the uncertainty and variability of the environmental impacts depending on the model assumptions and the process and transport parameters. Furthermore, we used the results from the Monte-Carlo simulations for a global sensitivity analysis based on a built-in function of *lca_algebraic*. It expresses the global sensitivity by the so-called Sobol indices (Sobol', 2001). While total Sobol indices also reflect the effect of parameter interactions, first-order Sobol indices only cover direct effects from individual parameter variability. The indices range from 0 to 1, and their sum equals 1. The uncertainty of impact assessment methods and background databases, such as ecoinvent, is not considered by *lca_algebraic* (Jolivet et al., 2021).

2.6. Parametrization and probability distributions

The uncertainty and sensitivity analyses were conducted based on parametrized life cycle inventories where probability distributions represented parameter value variability. A key advantage of parametrized inventories is that uncertainties for process flows, such as water, energy, and emissions, are not sampled independently. Instead, parametrized inventories consistently preserve correlations between processes and process flows. For example, a higher material flow in a machine can lead to an increased energy demand for its operation, which could not be accounted for if uncertainties for material and energy flows were sampled independently. The agrifootprint database only provided single parameter values without any information about their uncertainty. Therefore, we assumed agricultural production parameters and all parameters where only one value was collected to be fixed. If two estimates for a parameter could be found in the literature, we used a uniform distribution where the lower and higher values represented the minimum and maximum values of the distribution, respectively. If more than two estimates for a parameter value were obtained, we applied a triangular distribution where the median of the collected parameter values served as the mode and the lowest and highest collected values as the minimum and maximum of the distribution, respectively. We selected triangular distributions because they capture data skewness while avoiding assumptions about specific distribution shapes (e.g., Normal or Weibull) that could not be verified with limited data.

All processes before the defatting and protein extraction steps were only composed of one unit operation. In the case of defatting, inventories from existing studies were used, which provided the material and energy flows over the entire defatting step (see section 2.3). Therefore, parametrization yielded relatively simple equations for the above-mentioned unit processes. For example, Eq. 1 shows how the input of dried seeds required to produce 1 kg of dehulled seeds is expressed in a parametrized form.

$$\text{Input}_{\text{dry seeds}} = P_{\text{dehulling losses}} + 1 \quad (1)$$

where:

$\text{Input}_{\text{dry seeds}}$: Input of dry seeds [kg/kg dehulled seeds]

$P_{\text{dehulling losses}}$: Parameter for the losses in the process, e.g., hulls [kg/kg dehulled seeds]

Since the protein extraction processes were constructed in a bottom-up approach, the parametrized inventories included parameter values for the protein balance, material flows, and energy requirements of each piece of equipment. For example, Eq. 2 shows how the electricity consumption of a protein isolation process was generally expressed in a parametrized form.

$$E_{\text{ele}} = \frac{P_{\text{output protein}}}{P_{\text{protein recovery}} * P_{\text{input protein}}} * \sum_i^n (P_{m,i} * P_{\text{ele},i}) * (1 + P_{\text{ele.pumping}}) \quad (2)$$

where:

E_{ele} : Electricity demand of the protein isolation process [kWh/kg_{output}]

$P_{\text{output protein}}$: Parameter for the protein content in the output [kg/kg]

$P_{\text{protein recovery}}$: Parameter for the protein yield in the isolation process [–]

$P_{\text{input protein}}$: Parameter for the protein content in the input material [kg/kg]

$P_{m,i}$: Parameter for the relative mass flow in equipment *i* per kg input material [kg/kg]

$P_{\text{ele},i}$: Specific electricity demand per kg input into equipment *i* [kWh/kg]

$P_{\text{ele.pumping}}$: Electricity demand for pumping as a share of total demand [kWh/kWh]

By default, the Python libraries *brightway2* (Mutel, 2017) and *lca_algebraic* (Jolivet et al., 2021), which were used for the LCA calculations, can only process fixed allocation factors. Therefore, allocation factors had to be included as a parameter in the inventory to account for their uncertainty. Allocating a specific share of impacts to one co-product of a process is mathematically equivalent to allocating all impacts to this co-product but multiplying the amount of the product that is used in a downstream process by the same share. Hence, when the output of an upstream process was used as an input in another process of the foreground inventory, the required amount was multiplied by the respective allocation parameters. To account for allocation factors in the final production step, we added another process to the product system with an output of 1 kg of the final product and an input of 1 kg of the final product multiplied by the allocation factor. The same approach was taken to account for the uncertainty of protein contents in the final product, if a protein-based functional unit was used. All parameter values and parametrized equations can be found in SI2.

2.7. Transport

In the foreground model, transport was modelled probabilistically to account for uncertainty in the exact location of production areas, processing facilities, and points of use within countries. In other words, transport distances were modelled as parameters with probability distributions representing the variable distances between two countries. The approach is therefore well-suited for assessments that investigate the range of potential impacts from a production system where the exact locations of the production steps within a country are unknown. Regarding the mode of transport, we focused on maritime and road transport, which cumulatively account for 93 % of total freight transport in the European Union (Eurostat, 2025). We approximated the distribution of transport distances between any two European countries in three steps. First, we calculated the centroids of the smallest available administrative units in each country based on data from GADM (GADM, 2025). Second, we calculated the air distance between each pair of centroids in the two countries. Third, we multiplied the distances by an average detour factor of 1.2 to translate air distance into road distance

(Schnabel and Lohse, 2011). Further, we assumed that dried seeds and protein ingredients are generally transported by truck within continental Europe.

Intercontinental transport was modelled for the most relevant overseas suppliers of pea, soy, and wheat for the European plant protein market, namely Brazil, China, and the United States of America (see also section 2.1). First, we obtained the distribution of cultivation areas for each crop in each of the three countries from the International Food Policy Research Institute (International Food Policy Research Institute, 2010). Second, we calculated the air distance between each cultivation area and the closest major shipping port (Maritime safety office, 2025) for each crop and country. The transport distance from each cultivation area was weighted by its respective share of total production in the country and multiplied by the average detour factor of 1.2 to estimate transport distances by road (Schnabel and Lohse, 2011). Third, we calculated the shortest air distance from each of the smallest administrative units in Europe to the closest major shipping port in Europe (Maritime safety office, 2025) and also multiplied it by 1.2. Fourth, we estimated the sea distances between all considered European and overseas ports based on an online calculation tool (Ports.com, 2025). For each crop and country combination, e.g., soy from Brazil to Great Britain, we then weighted the distances between the European and overseas ports by the share of product delivered to the closest port in the exporting country and the share of administrative units that are closest to a specific European port (Eq. 3).

$$Dist_{sea,weighted,i,j,k} = Weights_{port,j} \times Weights_{cultivation,i,k} * Dist_{sea} \quad (3)$$

where:

$Dist_{sea,weighted,i,j,k}$: $n \times m$ matrix containing the weighted sea distances for transport of crop k between exporting country i and importing country j [m]

$Weights_{port,j}$: $n \times 1$ matrix containing the share of administrative units of country j that are closest to port $1:n$ in Europe [–]

$Weights_{cultivation,i,k}$: $1 \times m$ matrix containing the share of cultivation areas of crop k in country i that are closest to port $1:m$ [–]

$Dist_{sea}$: $n \times m$ matrix containing the sea distances between ports $1:n$ in Europe and ports $1:m$ in exporting country i [m]

\times : matrix multiplication

$*$: elementwise multiplication

Finally, it was necessary to summarize the resulting transport distance distributions between two countries by parametrized probability distributions to reduce the vast amount of data and make the distributions processible for the LCA model. Since no commonly used probability distribution accurately reflected most of the observed transport distance distributions, we decided to express all distributions by their mean and standard deviation. This necessary simplification erroneously implied a normal distribution and led to a certain inaccuracy in the results. By ignoring the multimodality and skewness of empirical distributions, the implied normal distributions could, e.g., underestimate extreme values while overestimating values close to the mean. Further, we assumed that processing facilities in Brazil, China, and the US are located near the cultivation areas so that the transport from cultivation to processing is negligible within these countries. This could lead to an underestimation of real transport distances if processing facilities were located further away from cultivation areas. For the production scenarios modelled in this study (Table S. 1), we assumed that all processing steps take place at the same location.

2.8. Impact assessment

Most LCA studies to date rely on global characterization factors for the impact assessment. This critically neglects regional differences in climatic conditions, population density, background concentrations of hazardous substances, flora, and fauna, among others. To account for region-specific preconditions, this study relied on regionalized impact

assessment methods for WS, PM-HI, and LU-BL together with the IPCC method for GW. They were selected for their maturity and relevance following recommendations from the Global Guidance for Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators (UNEP / SETAC, 2016). Climate impacts were quantified by the global warming potential over 100 years based on global characterization factors from the IPCC (IPCC, 2023). LU-BL was quantified with potentially disappeared fractions of species (PDF) based on country-specific characterization factors (Scherer et al., 2023). Impacts related to WS were assessed based on country-specific characterization factors according to the Available Water Remaining (AWARE) method (Boulay et al., 2018). Finally, PM-HI were quantified in disability adjusted life years (DALYs) based on average characterization factors from Oberschelp et al. (2020) at a spatial resolution of the 26 regions used in the IMAGE 3.0 model (Stehfest et al., 2014). The same four impact categories have also been used in the environmental assessment for the Global Resource Outlook by UNEP (UNEP, 2024). We implemented the regionalized impact assessment in Python according to previous work by Huo et al. (2024). Especially for agricultural processes, other impact categories such as acidification, eutrophication, and ecotoxicity are also relevant and widely used at a global resolution. Therefore, we additionally quantified environmental impacts based on the global characterization factors of the ReCiPe 2016 method (Huijbregts et al., 2017) to provide a more comprehensive overview of impact categories and allow for better comparisons with existing literature (see SI S.5). The endpoint results (Table SI S.6) confirmed the relevance of the selected impact categories for regionalized assessments as top contributors to ecosystem and human health impacts.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Overall impacts and their variability

Value chains of SPI, SPC, PPI, PPC, and WG for the European market show a high impact variability across products and provenances (Fig. 2). Generally, isolates show higher impacts than concentrates of the same crop per kilogram of product (Fig. 2). When a protein-based functional unit is applied, impacts are scaled, and the additional uncertainty from varying protein content is included in the resulting distributions. Consequently, differences between isolates and concentrates become smaller due to the higher protein contents of isolates. For certain value chains, maximum impacts from PPC (41–66 % protein) even exceed those of PPI (78–84 % protein) when calculated based on 1 kg of protein (Fig. 2).

Furthermore, we find that products sourced from European and US value chains tend to have lower impacts compared to products from China, except for WS of PPI and PPC in France (Fig. 2). For example, the WS caused by SPI and SPC is approximately 2 times higher in China compared to the US (Fig. 2c). On the one hand, this can be explained by different preconditions in the countries studied. China has a comparatively high population density, average background concentration of PM (Oberschelp et al., 2020), and average water scarcity (Boulay et al., 2018) compared to European countries and the US. Additionally, average crop yields are lower in China, which affects the land use and related impacts on biodiversity. Nevertheless, impact probability distributions overlap for most value chains of the same product (Fig. 2) due to variable process parameters such as the protein yield during protein extraction, energy efficiency, solvent use, and transport distance. Together, they can alter the impacts of individual value chains by a factor of 1.5 to 3. Incorporating uncertainties related to agricultural practices would likely further widen the resulting impact ranges.

There are noticeable trade-offs between impact categories due to different origins. For example, we find exceptionally high GW impacts (Fig. 2a) and LU-BL (Fig. 2d) for SPI (8.2–16.1 kgCO₂-eq/kg; 1.1–2.1 * 10⁻¹³ PDF/kg) and SPC (5.1–8.2 kgCO₂-eq/kg; 7.1 * 10⁻¹⁴–1.2 * 10⁻¹³ PDF/kg) from Brazilian soy due to deforestation, which is ongoing despite multiple mitigation efforts (Villoria et al., 2022). Based on

Fig. 2. The distribution of environmental impacts in terms of a) global warming (GW), b) particulate matter related health impacts (PM-HI), c) water stress (WS), and d) land use related biodiversity loss (LU-BL) caused by value chains of soy protein isolate (SPI), soy protein concentrate (SPC), pea protein isolate (PPI), pea protein concentrate (PPC), and wheat gluten (WG) for the European market. The system boundaries are cradle-to-gate, including transport to the country of use (Switzerland). The results are shown for 1 kg of product (filled, colored) and 1 kg of protein (dashed, grey). The two-letter country codes indicate the location of cultivation and processing, respectively. The results were obtained by Monte-Carlo simulations with 100'000 iterations. Absolute values can be found in Tables S.2–3 in SI1. Abbreviations: DALY – disability adjusted life years; PDF – potentially disappeared fraction of species; BR – Brazil; GB – Great Britain; CN – China; US – United States of America; NL – the Netherlands; DE – Germany; FR – France.

median values, these impacts are 2.5–3.6 and 10–13 times higher compared to the GW impacts and LU-BL of SPIs and SPCs from other value chains, respectively. At the same time, WS and PM-HI for SPI and SPC from Brazilian soy are among the lowest of all studied value chains (Fig. 2b&c). Similarly, PPI and PPC from France show the lowest GW impacts and PM-HI but the highest WS and LU-BL among European value chains (Fig. 2).

3.2. Contribution analysis

The resulting GW impacts are dominated by the cultivation and protein extraction stage (Fig. 3a). Apart from deforestation in Brazil, GW impacts from cultivation are driven by fertilizer production, the use of machinery, and direct dinitrogen monoxide emissions from fertilizer application. GW impacts from the extraction stage are mainly linked to thermal energy requirements for heating and preservation, except for dry fractionated PPC, which does not require an energy-intensive drying step (Fig. 3a). Transport contributes between 3 and 23 % to the GW impacts of the average results (Fig. 3a). Thereby, the largest contributions of transport can be observed for value chains where larger volumes of raw materials are shipped instead of extracted protein powders (compare, e.g., SPI and SPC from US-NL to US-US in Fig. 3a).

PM-HI are mainly linked to cultivation. Consequently, PM-HI are generally lowest for soy-based products because soybeans have the highest protein yields and thus require less input material per kg of extracted protein. Besides, the contribution analysis shows that overseas transport is responsible for 19–43 % of PM-HI for SPI and SPC from BR and the US, due to the comparatively low impacts in the cultivation and processing stages in these value chains (Fig. 3b). We identify irrigation as the main cause for WS of soy-based products from the US and China, WG from China, and pea-based products from France (Fig. 3c). WS of non-irrigated value chains is estimated to be in the order of 0.001–0.2 m³-equivalents per kg of product compared to 0.3–34.3 m³-equivalents for irrigated value chains (Fig. 2c). LU-BL is mainly caused by the cultivation phase due to the land requirement of crop cultivation (Fig. 3d).

3.3. Global sensitivity analysis

We calculated Sobol indices based on the Monte-Carlo simulations to investigate the global sensitivity of the model results with respect to the applied processing, transport, and LCA model parameters. The indices indicate the relative contribution (0–1) of each parameter to the overall output variance of the model. Note that this analysis focused on protein processing. Therefore, uncertainties in cultivation practices, such as yields, fertilizer, and pesticide application, were not included. The calculation of first-order (Fig. 4) and total Sobol indices (Fig. S.6) produced almost identical results. This indicates that parameter interactions have a minimal influence on the model sensitivity compared to direct effects by parameter variability shown in Fig. 4.

The results across all impact categories are highly sensitive to parameters related to the protein balance in the protein extraction step, i. e., the protein content of the input and output material, and the protein recovery (Fig. 4). These parameters define the amount of input material that is required for protein extraction and thus scale all upstream processes, including the cultivation phase. For example, the lower protein yields of isolation processes mean that larger quantities of raw materials are needed per kg of SPI and PPI, which leads to higher impacts from the cultivation phase compared to SPC and PPC, respectively (Fig. 3).

Because of the large contribution of thermal energy to the GW impacts of wet extraction processes (Fig. 3a), the model results are sensitive to process parameters related to the specific thermal energy requirements of heating, drying, and evaporation equipment, and the dry matter content in the input material of spray dryers (Fig. 4). Similarly, processes with high electricity demands like milling and grinding contribute to the variance in WS and PM-HI (Fig. 4) due to hydropower

production and power plants based on fossil fuels, respectively.

For extraction processes with valuable side streams, such as the starch fractions in PPI and WG production, the model results across all impact categories are sensitive to the price ratios between the different outputs (Fig. 4), which were used to allocate impacts between multi-output processes. Similarly, the starch content in wheat flour is a relevant process parameter because it influences the impact allocation between WG and wheat starch. To a lesser degree, the model results are sensitive to price ratios applied for impact allocation in upstream processes such as wheat milling and soy defatting (Fig. 4).

Finally, the influence of varying transport distances on the sensitivity of the model results strongly depends on the combination of impact category and value chain (Fig. 4). In general, the probabilistic sampling of transport distances between cultivation, processing, and point-of-use (see methods for details) contributes most to the model variance for value chains with low overall impacts. Examples are PM-HI of soy-based value chains as well as WS of most wheat- and pea-based value chains (Fig. 3). However, even for GW, where transport contributes not more than 23 % to the overall impacts (Fig. 3), transport distances can be the most sensitive model parameter for certain value chains (Fig. 4). This can be explained by the large variability of possible distances between two randomly chosen locations within specific countries. For example, the minimum and maximum distances between France (FR) and the Netherlands (NL) are 68 and 815 km, respectively. Consequently, impacts from transport can vary by more than a factor of ten.

3.4. Comparison of findings with existing literature

This is the first study to assess regionalized impacts for plant proteins. Therefore, the findings can only be compared to existing literature based on the GW impacts and the impacts obtained by the ReCiPe 2016 method (Table S.5). While we could not find data for SPC, previously reported GW impacts per kg of SPI, PPI, PPC, and WG are 1.1–7.8 kgCO₂-eq (Thrane et al., 2017), 4.2 kgCO₂-eq (Lie-Piang et al., 2021), 0.4–1.9 kgCO₂-eq (Allotey et al., 2024; Desiderio et al., 2023; Lie-Piang et al., 2021), and 1.55 kgCO₂-eq (Deng et al., 2013), respectively. Apart from WG, for which we find two to three times higher GW impacts, these values correspond well with our results (Fig. 2a). Similarly, previous results for PPI, SPI, and PPC based on ReCiPe impact categories mostly fall within the ranges presented here. Exceptions are human toxicity and ionizing radiation impacts of PPI, and values for ozone depletion of PPC reported by Desiderio et al. (2023) and Lie-Piang et al. (2021), respectively. They are one to two orders of magnitude higher than the values found here. As for GW, the impacts of WG found by Deng et al. (2013) are well below our findings for all ReCiPe impact categories but marine eutrophication and water use.

3.5. Contextualization of the findings

In their comprehensive meta-analysis, Poore and Nemecek (2018) reported 5th–95th percentile GW impacts of 76–1350 kgCO₂-eq, 120–300 kgCO₂-eq, 43–150 kgCO₂-eq, and 23–120 kgCO₂-eq per kg of protein in beef, lamb, pig, and poultry meat, respectively. These values are all well above the 1.5–17.1 kgCO₂-eq per kg of pure plant protein we find here (Fig. 2a). In terms of WS, Poore and Nemecek (2018) reported median impacts of 4.4 m³-eq, 2.6 m³-eq, 542 m³-eq, and 3.3 m³-eq per kg of protein in beef, lamb, pig, and poultry meat, respectively. These values are comparable to the median WS of 0.65–35.8 m³-eq per kg of pure plant protein we estimate for products based on irrigated crops (Fig. 2c). However, the variability of WS is vast in both studies and linked to variable production systems and climatic conditions. Both studies applied economic allocation principles and relied on characterization factors from IPCC and AWARE for GW and WS, respectively. Nevertheless, there are methodological differences. The most relevant being the system boundary, which includes transport to retailers and final product packaging in the study by Poore and Nemecek (2018). Although

Fig. 3. The contribution to overall impacts by each subprocess for a) global warming (GW), b) particulate matter related health impacts (PM-HI), c) water stress (WS), and d) land use related biodiversity loss (LU-BL) caused by value chains of soy protein isolate (SPI), soy protein concentrate (SPC), pea protein isolate (PPI), pea protein concentrate (PPC), and wheat gluten (WG) for the European market. The two-letter country codes indicate the location of cultivation and processing, respectively. The contributions represent averages based on the results of Monte-Carlo simulations with 100'000 runs per kg product as shown in Fig. 2. Absolute values can be found in Table S.4 in SI1. Abbreviations: DALY – disability adjusted life years; PDF – potentially disappeared fraction of species; BR – Brazil; GB – Great Britain; CN – China; US – United States of America; NL – the Netherlands; DE – Germany; FR – France.

	GW	PM-HI	WS	LU-BL
Wheat Gluten (WG)				
Electricity pin mill	0.01 - 0.01	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.06	0.00 - 0.01
Heat ring dryer	0.09 - 0.15	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.03	0.00 - 0.29
Wheat gluten price ratio A starch	0.17 - 0.29	0.26 - 0.28	0.10 - 0.27	0.18 - 0.26
Wheat gluten price ratio B starch	0.11 - 0.16	0.15 - 0.17	0.07 - 0.15	0.11 - 0.17
Wheat gluten protein in	0.10 - 0.13	0.23 - 0.23	0.06 - 0.24	0.12 - 0.24
Wheat gluten starch content flour	0.05 - 0.09	0.12 - 0.12	0.03 - 0.12	0.07 - 0.12
Wheat milling electricity	0.01 - 0.02	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.08	0.00 - 0.02
Wheat milling price ratio	0.04 - 0.06	0.13 - 0.14	0.00 - 0.15	0.07 - 0.15
Transport distances	0.02 - 0.40	0.00 - 0.02	0.00 - 0.59	0.00 - 0.24
Soy protein isolate (SPI)				
Heat spray dryer	0.08 - 0.53	0.00 - 0.05	0.00 - 0.03	0.00 - 0.31
SPI protein in	0.02 - 0.14	0.10 - 0.18	0.02 - 0.18	0.09 - 0.17
SPI protein recovery	0.08 - 0.57	0.39 - 0.67	0.10 - 0.67	0.34 - 0.67
SPI solvent ratio	0.01 - 0.05	0.00 - 0.19	0.00 - 0.05	0.00 - 0.01
dm content spray dryer	0.04 - 0.25	0.00 - 0.03	0.00 - 0.30	0.00 - 0.14
Transport distances	0.02 - 0.10	0.00 - 0.36	0.00 - 0.46	0.00 - 0.09
Soy protein concentrate (SPC)				
Electricity grinding	0.00 - 0.01	0.00 - 0.08	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.00
Heat evaporation ethanol	0.01 - 0.11	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.08
SPC energy heating	0.01 - 0.07	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.05
SPC protein in	0.19 - 0.42	0.12 - 0.42	0.12 - 0.43	0.24 - 0.43
SPC protein out	0.10 - 0.24	0.06 - 0.25	0.07 - 0.26	0.14 - 0.25
SPC protein recovery	0.03 - 0.07	0.02 - 0.07	0.02 - 0.08	0.04 - 0.07
Soy defatting oil production	0.01 - 0.08	0.02 - 0.10	0.00 - 0.10	0.05 - 0.10
Soy defatting price ratio	0.01 - 0.08	0.02 - 0.09	0.00 - 0.10	0.05 - 0.10
Transport distances	0.06 - 0.40	0.02 - 0.65	0.00 - 0.75	0.00 - 0.33
Pea protein isolate (PPI)				
Heat spray dryer	0.10 - 0.27	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.06	0.18 - 0.22
PPI price ratio	0.42 - 0.60	0.57 - 0.58	0.48 - 0.61	0.40 - 0.44
PPI protein in	0.03 - 0.07	0.14 - 0.15	0.07 - 0.15	0.08 - 0.08
PPI protein recovery	0.04 - 0.12	0.22 - 0.24	0.11 - 0.24	0.12 - 0.13
dm content spray dryer	0.04 - 0.12	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.03	0.09 - 0.10
Transport distances	0.01 - 0.08	0.00 - 0.02	0.00 - 0.20	0.03 - 0.08
Pea protein concentrate (PPC)				
PPC protein in	0.03 - 0.07	0.06 - 0.07	0.00 - 0.07	0.03 - 0.05
PPC protein out	0.08 - 0.17	0.17 - 0.18	0.00 - 0.18	0.09 - 0.12
PPC protein recovery	0.31 - 0.64	0.65 - 0.68	0.00 - 0.67	0.34 - 0.44
Pea milling electricity	0.00 - 0.02	0.00 - 0.00	0.00 - 0.60	0.00 - 0.12
Transport distances	0.03 - 0.52	0.00 - 0.04	0.01 - 0.88	0.35 - 0.49

Fig. 4. Summary of the range of first-order Sobol indices that were obtained from modelling the 19 protein value chains for the European market based on Monte-Carlo simulations with 100'000 runs. The indices (0–1) express the relative contribution of each parameter to the overall output variance of the model for the global warming impacts (GW), particulate matter-related health impacts (PM-HI), water stress (WS), and land use-related biodiversity loss (LU-BL). High Sobol indices indicate high contributions of the respective parameters to the overall model variance, i.e., high parameter sensitivity. Here, only parameters are listed where the Sobol index for at least one impact category exceeded the limit of 0.05. A complete overview of all parameters can be found in Figs. S.1–5 in SI1. The functional unit was 1 kg of product.

suitable as a reference, a direct comparison between plant proteins and meat should be avoided. Plant proteins must undergo further processing together with other ingredients to obtain an edible meat substitute. Additionally, a comparison based on mass or protein might not sufficiently account for the dietary role of meat, e.g., as an important supplier of micronutrients (Green et al., 2022).

To put the results for the less tangible impact categories of PM-HI and LU-BL into perspective, it is best to consider the annual exports of WG from the EU and China, which are currently at around 330'000 and 183'000 tons, respectively (United Nations Statistics Division, 2025). Based on the impacts of WG, we present here (Fig. 2), this corresponds to a combined health burden from particulate matter emissions of 2300 to 4000 disability adjusted life years. Similarly, the combined impacts from land use on biodiversity cause a fraction of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ of species to potentially disappear globally. In comparison, at a global scale, 120 million DALY were caused by outdoor air pollution in 2021 (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME), 2021) and almost 16 % of terrestrial plant and invertebrate species were found to be at risk of extinction in the long run (Scherer et al., 2023).

3.6. Model uncertainties and limitations

Modelling decisions can significantly influence LCA results (Siegrist et al., 2023). In the present assessment, this is demonstrated by the

example of economic allocation. Price ratios between the final protein ingredients and co-products cause around half of the model variation for PPI and WG (Fig. 4) due to their high variability. These findings confirm the sensitivity towards market price fluctuations, which is often criticized despite the widespread use of economic allocation (Kyttä et al., 2022). Another critical modelling decision is the functional unit (Siegrist et al., 2023). Fig. 2 illustrates how dry-matter protein contents act as scaling factors for our results when switching from a mass- to a protein-based FU. In fact, it even alters the order of the most impactful products for certain impact categories. Thus, the analysis could be extended in the future to include more comprehensive nutritional FUs, such as the Nutrient-Rich Food index (Drewnowski and Fulgoni, 2008).

Due to the complexity of the production systems, the model has several limitations. First, we had to hold many parameter values constant or model them by uniform distributions because only one or two data points could be identified in the literature (SI 2). Hence, more data would be needed to estimate parameter distributions and improve overall model accuracy. Furthermore, the model does not cover the uncertainty of individual data sources, background databases, and impact assessment methods. While most of the latter and the agrifootprint database did not provide uncertainty estimates, the use of uncertainty values from ecoinvent was not possible in the parametric calculation tools of lca_algebraic (Jolivet et al., 2021). Furthermore, the random sampling of uncertainty values from ecoinvent is known to lead

to unrealistic negative impacts because in- and outputs of, e.g., water and land use flows, are not linked in the database (Brightway Developers, 2025).

While our model results reflect different agricultural practices across countries, the variability in cultivation practices should be considered at a sub-country level in the future due to agriculture's large contribution to overall impacts (Fig. 3). We expect that this will further increase the overall model uncertainty. Ideally, agricultural processes would also be parametrized to account for links between, e.g., fertilizer and pesticide applications, crop yield, and field emissions. The selected regionalized impact assessment methods should be applied at a higher spatial resolution in future assessments, especially for large countries such as Brazil, China, and the US, as they can have a significant influence (Pfister and Bayer, 2014). Subject to the availability of robust characterization factors at the country or sub-country level, the assessment may be expanded in the future to include additional regional impact assessment methods. Finally, the model captures the influence of certain process parameters (e.g., solvent temperature and dry matter content of feed in spray drying) and material flows on energy consumption and impact allocation. At the same time, the influence of processing parameters, material, and energy flows on the protein contents of final products was unknown and could not be modelled. For example, a higher amount of solvent could lead to an increased protein content after wet extraction. Similarly, the correlation between product quality and price could not be modelled due to a lack of data. Ignoring such correlations can lead to an under- or overestimation of the output variance, depending on the signs of the partial derivatives and covariance (Groen and Heijungs, 2017).

3.7. Implications

From a methodological perspective, the findings underscore the value of comprehensive studies with an extensive sensitivity and uncertainty analysis (Smetana et al., 2023) that incorporate and complement the knowledge from case studies. In particular, the findings highlight the need to consider regional differences in, e.g., crop cultivation and energy production systems, as well as variability in process parameters (Fig. 2) (Hellweg and Canals, 2014). Furthermore, the findings illustrate how regionalized impact assessment methods can elevate the relevance of results by incorporating specific damage potentials and background concentrations (Boulay et al., 2018; Oberschelp et al., 2020; Scherer et al., 2023). For example, the higher impacts of LU on biodiversity in Brazil, China, and France would have been overlooked by global impact assessment methods (Scherer et al., 2023). The same applies to the higher potential for WS and PM-HI in China due to increased water scarcity (Boulay et al., 2018) and high population densities and background concentrations of PM (Oberschelp et al., 2020), respectively (Fig. 2 b-d). Finally, we find that transport contributes up to 23 % and 43 % to the average results for GW impacts and PM-HI of certain value chains, respectively (Fig. 3). These contributions could vary substantially between model runs of the same value chain, as indicated by the high model sensitivity with respect to transport distances (Fig. 4). This emphasizes the value of probabilistic transport modelling in capturing the range of potential impacts if the exact process locations are unknown.

From an application perspective, there are four main takeaways. First and foremost, users of plant proteins, such as meat substitute manufacturers, should be aware of their supply chains and carefully consider the origin of their ingredients, given the large influence of the geographical location on environmental impacts (Fig. 2). At a consumer level, more transparency about the origin of plant proteins in final products is required to allow for informed decisions. Second, environmental impacts (across all products and impact categories) largely depend on the protein content in the input material (Fig. 4). Therefore, protein-rich crops and varieties should be prioritized and further improved for protein extraction. Third, producers of plant protein

ingredients should focus on achieving a high protein yield due to its large influence on the required amount of input material, which scales the impacts of all upstream processes (Fig. 4). For example, albumin fractions could be recovered from the aqueous fraction after isoelectric precipitation to increase overall yields. Finally, the results show that heating energy from non-renewable resources is a major driver for GW impacts of wet extraction and preservation processes (Fig. 3a). This energy demand could be reduced by waste heat recovery through high-temperature heat pumps (Arpagaus et al., 2018), adapted drying methods that can handle a higher input solids content, or by directly using a protein paste instead of powders for subsequent product manufacturing. In the long term, the remaining energy demand should be met with renewable energy sources.

4. Conclusions

The parametric LCA modelling platform and processing data can readily be used to produce LCAs for value chains of plant proteins in the European context. For wider application, the model should be extended to cover cultivation outside of Europe, the US, China, and Brazil, and consider parameter interactions and uncertainty in the cultivation phase at a sub-country level. The suggested probabilistic modelling approach for transport may find applications in value chain modelling and sustainability assessments beyond plant protein production, whenever the exact locations of processes are unknown. For this purpose, the applied concept should be extended to include different modes of transport and vehicles and reach global coverage. Furthermore, the parametric structure of the model is well-suited for applications in prospective and scenario-based LCAs. It could thus be extended to analyze emerging technologies for protein processing in the future.

The presented case studies for SPI, SPC, PPI, PPC, and WG provide harmonized, i.e., methodically aligned, and robust estimates for regionalized impacts of PM-HI, WS, and LU-BL, along with GW impacts at extensive spatial coverage. An important takeaway for LCA practitioners is the added value of regionalized assessment methods, as well as the crucial role of uncertainty and sensitivity analyses in testing the robustness of results and model sensitivity with respect to modelling decisions such as the functional unit and allocation principles.

Based on the presented findings, we conclude that refined plant proteins are an environmentally sustainable alternative to animal-based protein sources despite energy-intensive processing steps for protein concentration and isolation. At the same time, more transparency along plant protein value chains is needed, and technological improvements could further reduce their environmental impacts. Thereby, key leverage points are the protein content in raw materials, extraction yields, renewable energy sources, and transport.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Armin Siegrist: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Joseph Dimpler:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Jing Huo:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology. **Ashley Green:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Paride Azzari:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Joachim Baumann:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Moritz Goessler:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Stephan Pfister:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Alexander Mathys:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Code availability

The code written for the presented model is available on GITHUB (https://github.com/siegarmi/Parametric_LCA_plant_proteins).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2025.12.010>.

Data availability

All raw data produced by the Monte-Carlo simulations are available in the data repository <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-c-000791691>. All data can be reproduced using the model code.

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